

TYPES OF VEGETATIVE PROPAGATION OF ORNAMENTAL TREE-SHRUB PLANTS IN LANDSCAPING

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Annotation: since the Republic of Karakalpakstan is a sharply continental sharaoit, the choice of an assortment of tree-shrub species is one of the important tasks when greening cities and villages. Growing sprouts propagated from non-standard, random seeds in nurseries for greenery purposes is not suitable. That is why this article provides information on methods and types of vegetative propagation of ornamental tree-shrub plants in landscaping.

Keywords: tree, shrub, greenery, vegetative, green pencil, winter pencil, germination, reproduction, factors.

Today, large-scale construction work and improvement activities are carried out in all cities and villages of our country. This means that around such objects it will be necessary to carry out greening work to meet the requirements of the Times. To do this, it will be necessary to grow ornamental deciduous and coniferous tree seedlings, which are suitable for local conditions and grow freely in dry climates, taken care of giving shape from an early age. To do this, it is necessary to expand the network of ornamental nurseries with a high agricultural culture, increase the amount and quality of seedlings of ornamental tree-shrub species grown in them on the basis of innovative ideas and advanced experiments.

The range of plant species is limited for the existing Greening sector in the Karalpakstan ambiti, and it is important to breed and improve it. Growing sprouts propagated from non-standard, random seeds in nurseries for greenery purposes is not suitable. Particular attention should be paid to the planting of such species as Virginian spruce, Crimean Pine, Oriental biota species, Linden, White Acacia, beautiful Catalpa, shumtol, Maple, Japanese cedar and ornamental Mulberry from deciduous trees from Dragonfly trees, suitable for planting in cities, resistant and long-lived and with a valuable ornamental appearance.

When propagating tree and Bush seedlings in a vegetative way, vegetative fragments consist in creating new young plants in Aloxi based on the trunk, roots, branches and other parts. Vegetative propagation of plants is used in many cases in the construction of artificial Woodlands. It is applied to the products created in the nursery when Greening populated areas and also for planting.

Vegetative propagation helps to cope with the difficulties that arise when propagating from seeds. With this method, this method is very applicable in the adaptation of some types

of trees in the existing district and provides the basis for the transition of its valuable biological-economic hereditary signs from the next generation to the next. The advantage of vegetative propagation is that as early as the first year of seedlings, the plant is growing rapidly, that is, seedlings propagated by this method in relation to seed reproduction enter a fast harvest.

It is understood that the vegetative propagation of trees and shrubs in natural conditions occurs in most cases in the under-Root direction, new young plants constantly appear from the Mudder shoots on the rain rhizomes.

Natural vegetative reproduction is active in the following tree-shrub plants: Poplar, oblepixa, ligustrum, raspberries, blackberries, totim, Willow, na'matak, barberry. Jida, yulghun, lianas.

Reproduction in an artificial vegetative way is divided into species as follows:

Reproduction without partial separation of mother plants:

- reproduction from rhizome;
- -from the top of the ground-reproduction in the parchish method.
- Extract and propagate from the mother tree. This method is as follows;
- wooden branch pencil;
- pencil from the root;
- based on green pencil in summer;
- separation and maintenance of Root bački.

Reproduction without separating the mother trees and its part. Root sprouting is a type of plant that has sprouted from a healthy root. This is a multiplication from a root in which the Sprout is horizontal, that is, flat under the ground. It is necessary to infuse the underground root to form a soil germination, where the root will be deeper than 5 cm below the ground, some sprouts that are located more under the root part will grow and develop energetically. Cuttings from the root it is a type of plantable product from 0.5 cm to 1.5 cm. The work on the preparation of the product begins during the period of bargi Khazan in the morning of the autumn season.

Reproduction using winter and summer green cuttings. The preparation of summer (green) and winter (twig) cuttings will depend on:

- the amount of water in pencils;
- substrate composition;
- weather condition;
- effect of light;
- maternal tree age;
- shelf life;
- the age of the rod from which the pencil is made;
- rod length;
- tree type and varieties.

Rod pencils are placed in 500 pencils 5x4 cm or 1 sq. With the sand moist, the relative humidity is 90%, the temperature should not exceed 30°C. Green branches take root in work for 1 month. In our conditions, reproduction from winter cuttings is of much greater importance in the production of Forestry. Many tree species are propagated by this method, such as poplar, willow, Maple, yulghun, jiyda, Mulberry, etc. Winter cuttings are made from twigs of one year or two. The pencil is taken from young twigs from the sheepskin part of the

comb. Planting cuttings is different, the rule is done with weapons (hoe, tesha, waist.) The large part of the cuttings is buried under the soil, the sludge on the top of the soil can remain up to 1-2 cm.

Reproduction from Green cuttings. Among the methods of vegetative propagation, propagation from blue cuttings is of great importance, which in turn is a good method for growing undeveloped seedlings in difficult conditions. Mainly from coniferous trees, this method has a good effect. When making cuttings from these tree species, it is necessary that the STEM has an external appearance, that is, the pencil is flexible, non-breaking, well-grown, from a soft branch, light green shiny. The best of the cuttings, which can be obtained from coniferous trees, are found in wood-poplar trees. Pencil requires a length of 5-7 cm.

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